

CLASSROOM PRACTICES FOR BUILDING CONCEPTUAL UNDERSTANDING IN MATHEMATICS

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Abstract

Mathematics classroom practices mostly consider procedural fluency. But for the deeper understanding it is important to foster the mathematical processes by organizing various activities in the classroom. For each mathematical process, a teacher should play a crucial role to arrange such challenging tasks where each student will become active participant and deepen their conceptual understanding with dynamic classroom discourse. Such classrooms will transform the pedagogy from rote memorization to Mathematical proficiency.

Keywords: *Procedural fluency, Conceptual Understanding, Mathematical Processes, Mathematical Proficiency, Classroom practices*

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Introduction

An India-centred education system expected by the National Education Policy 2019 guides the stakeholders to transform our nation sustainably into an equitable and vibrant knowledge society with deeper conceptual understanding, by providing high quality education to all. Traditional Mathematics instruction mostly focus on content and rote memorization of mathematical steps for solution only, which does not support learners to have complete conceptual understanding. It provides procedural fluency by drilling.

Classroom Practices for Conceptual Understanding

National Research Council (NRC) 2001. in their report entitled Adding It Up: Helping Children

Learn Mathematics has given the term Mathematical Proficiency. This proficiency is possible only when the classroom practices consider the mathematical processes. As highlighted in Principles to Actions (National Council of Teachers of Mathematics, 2014), “An excellent mathematics program requires effective teaching that engages students in meaningful learning through individual and collaborative experiences that promote their ability to make sense of mathematical ideas and reason mathematically” (p. 5). This discussion highlights the ways of classroom practices, mathematical processes and the role of a mathematics teacher to be mathematical proficient student through instruction. Such mathematical instruction not only enable the student to demonstrate procedural knowledge in mathematics but also reflects a student's ability to reason in settings involving the careful application of concept definitions, relations, or representations of either. This type of reflection demonstrates the Conceptual Understanding. However, National Council of Mathematics Teachers – NCTM (2013) underlines the process of classroom practices for Mathematics should be oriented to a conceptual understanding.

In such classroom practices, role of a teacher is to encourage students to constantly examine their own thinking.

A teacher should focus five mathematical processes which are given by NCTM (2000). These processes lead to develop Conceptual Understanding are as follows:

1. Mathematical Communication
2. Mathematical Reasoning
3. Mathematical Connection
4. Mathematical Representation
5. Problem Solving

For effective Mathematics classroom to build conceptual understanding, the Mathematical Processes and the key components of classroom practices are given as below:

1. Mathematical Communication

A teacher should

- Give the background information such as vocabulary, at the start of the topic
- Introduce new terminology in a variety of ways.
- Encourage students to use correct mathematical language & symbols.

- Use literacy strategies for mathematical concept to help students to make sense of what they read & see.
- Facilitate students' learning through math-talk.

2. Mathematical Reasoning

A teacher should

- Provide feedback to an individual student during the learning process.
- Try to elicit incorrect ideas from the weaker students during the whole class work.
- Pose open-ended questions and challenging task in a group to promote reasoning skill.
- Encourage students to analyze and evaluate others mathematical thinking and strategies.
- Develop investigations about different concepts of math through heuristic method.
- Force justification with procedural fluency while solving math exercise or making a mathematical argument.
- Provide mathematical proofs by unfolding the proposition.

3. Mathematical Connection

A teacher should

- Expose the mathematical concepts.
- Encourage students to actively process in peer group.
- Allow such classroom discourse in which mathematical ideas/concepts get explored from multiple perspectives.
- Guide students, how different mathematical ideas are interrelated while solving different problems.
- Ask students to connect mathematical concepts with real world.
- Provide challenging tasks in which students apply mathematical concepts in context outside the textbook content.
- Teach different mathematical concepts with considering hierarchy of concepts.

4. Mathematical Representation

A teacher should

- Display the samples of student's work.
- Use different mathematical presentations to clarify various concepts.

- Encourage students to use various representations to communicate mathematical concepts.
- Give directions to convert the given information in different mathematical presentations.
- Prefer different modes of presentations for conceptual clarity.

5. Problem Solving

A teacher should

- Give a chance to the students to create alternative ways for a solution of a given mathematical problem.
- Encourage students to reflect on the process of mathematical problem solving.
- Demand only the procedural fluency while solving problem.
- Enable students to make mathematical conjectures for different mathematical concepts.
- Solve problem sets as per the need of the students.
- Restrict students from following their strategies for solving problem.

Conclusion

The mentioned classroom practices helpful to foster each mathematical process and support to accomplish the vision of NEP 2019. The National Education Policy 2019 envisages a new pedagogical structure for school Education. It forces such classroom instruction which must be relevant to the needs and interests of learners at different developmental stages and gives deep conceptual understanding. To manage such ways of instruction in a mathematics classroom that help students to develop mathematical proficiency is really a pedagogical challenge but an it is an inevitable shift.

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